

Enhanced Public Secondary School Funding Through Budget Planning and Implementation in Imo State: the Role of Principals

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ABSTRACT

This study discussed the enhanced public secondary school funding through budget planning and implementation in Imo State. The study answered two research questions and tested two null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The research design adopted for this study was a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was made up of all 460 public junior and senior secondary school principals from 302 secondary schools of the six educational zones in Imo State. There was no sampling due to the manageable size of the population. The instrument used for data collection was a researcher made rating scale titled "Principals Instrument in Budget Planning and Implementation Scale" (PIBPIS) with 20 items validated by experts. Cronbach alpha and SPSS version 20 was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which gave a reliability of 0.80. Mean and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions, while a t-test of SPSS version 20 was used to test the null hypotheses formulated for the study. The findings of the study revealed that principals of public secondary schools in Imo State are involved in school budget preparation to a low extent and in the effective use of school budgets to enhance funding. Based on the findings, some recommendations were made that the government and the school board should involve the principals in budget planning. The Secondary Education Management Board should make sure that principals defend their budget with their bursar annually. They should equip the school with adequate funds to maintain the school. The audit section of the board should make sure principals record all financial transactions.

Key Words: Budget Planning, Implementation, Funding, Secondary Education, Principals of Secondary Schools.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education remains the vehicle for social economic development and social mobilization in any society. Secondary education is a link between primary and tertiary education. It provides opportunity for a child to acquire additional knowledge skills, and traits beyond the primary level. According to the national policy on education revised edition [2013], the objectives of the secondary education is to produce a useful living individual within the society and preparation of students for tertiary education.

Secondary school funding is crucial for the education system and requires effective budget planning and implementation (Nwokocha, 2015). Funding has been identified as an indispensable instrument. This is because funding serves as the life-wire for the management and administration of most sectors of the economy including the educational sector. It is based on this fact that UNESCO recommended that 26% of the annual budget of any nation should be set aside for the administration and management of the educational sector, (Nwafor, Uchendu and Akani ,2015), quoted (Odia and Omofonmwan).

Without a well-planned budget, secondary schools will struggle to make any long-term financial decisions. Consequently, they won't be able to allocate resources based on organizational

needs and objectives and run the risk of descending into deficit. It can also save a lot of the time and stress associated with surprise financial shortfalls. Good budgeting also leads to better educational outcomes. It gives schools more scope to respond to curriculum changes and allocate resources where they are needed most.

The secondary school principals' make sure that the environment is safe for all students and staff members. They help teachers maximize their teaching potentials. It is the sole responsibility of the school principals as the head of the school to identify areas of need such as inadequate funding, inadequate/decay infrastructural facilities, inadequate instructional materials, wastage, negative attitude of teachers, low quality students-intake and poor academic performance of students. It follows that the secondary school principals should exhibit good and acceptable budget implementation in order to enhance funds to achieve the objectives of secondary education (Undie, 2016).

However, to ensure judicious spending of funds and accountability, school administrators (principals) should plan and prepare budget for their schools. Their involvement in budget planning enhance funding by fostering collaboration with the stakeholders. Their knowledge of the school needs make sure funds are directed where impactful. It prevents misappropriation of funds, avoid wasteful use while ensuring preservation of the school values. The effective utilization of resource goes a long way to enhance funding and contributing` to the success of schools.

Oboegbulem, and Kalu (2013), Ozara (2012), Nwokocha, Afianmagbon, and Emetarom (2014), and Chukwu, Ezepue, Ogunji, Igba, and Nduka, (2019) carried out research on budget preparation and administrative effectiveness of secondary school principals. To the best of knowledge of the researchers, none of these studies were carried out in Imo State, hence the need for this study to fill the gap. The study aims to examine the extent to which principals are involved in budget planning and implementation for enhanced public secondary school funding in Imo State. This will help address laxity in teachers, inadequate teaching materials, decaying infrastructures, and poor academic performance.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study focuses on enhanced public secondary school funding through budget planning and implementation in Imo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain the extent to which:

1. Principals participate in school budget preparation.
2. Principals are involved in effective use of school budget to enhance funding in public secondary schools.

2. THEORITICAL REVIEW

System Theory (1940)

Systems Theory as was propounded by Bertalanff, is a conceptual framework based on the principle that the component parts of the system that can best be understood in the content of the relationship with each other and with other system. System is a collection of interrelated parts which form some whole. System focuses on the arrangement of relations between the parts connect them into a whole. According to this theory, what affects one part, affects the other parts in the system and its environment. Connecting the theory to the topic of the research it is important to note that school budgeting is not a one-man business, rather it is a collective

responsibility of both the controlling unit (school management board) and the real implementers of the budget (principals and teachers). All of them form a synergy to plan the school budget. When one group of these persons among them is left out, the actual implementation of the budget will definitely be hampered. This portrays the school as a system, its products and the community is the sub-system. That is to say that for actual implementation of the budget to enhanced funding and increase academic performance, the principals must be fully involved in the planning of school budgets. Therefore, open system theory best suit the study as it sought to ascertain how principals' could enhanced fund through budget planning and implementation in the secondary school in Imo State.

Management By Objectives (MBO) Model 1954

Management by objectives was developed by Drucker. Is a model geared towards helping managers to set achievable goals. Management by objective places objectives of management of a system as a central focus in determining what is to be done, how and when it is to be done, who is to carry out what task and by what means tasks must be done and performance assessed. Management by objectives is a managerial device that formalizes institutionalize joint goal-setting between superior and sub-ordinate, which also allows the focusing of performance appraisal on results of behaviour rather than on the procedures by which the results are achieved. Management by objectives is therefore rooted on this study because the essence of school budgeting is to actualize the educational objectives. The practice of taking employees into confidence in decision-making and goal setting which management by objectives advocates bring about active participation, commitment and dedication of duty of all organizational members which planning implementation of budget in school administration encourages. The practice of taking employees into confidence in decision-making and goal setting which management by objectives advocates bring about active participation, commitment and dedication of duty of all organizational members which planning implementation of budget in school administration encourages. Management by objective concurred with the study as it sought to evaluate how principals' could enhanced fund through budget planning and implementation in public secondary schools in Imo State.

According to Hariyant (2015), one tool used to assess managers' performance is the budget. According to behavioural planning theory, the budgeting process is one action that managers feel will have a beneficial influence in the form of improved performance. Using a descriptive survey design, Asiegbu and Onyali (2019) investigated the issues and reasons behind inadequate budget preparation in secondary schools in the Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State. According to their results, the majority of administrators embezzle school cash, and some principals and personnel do not participate in the budget planning process. The review is similar to the present study as the directions was on secondary school Budgeting with the same research design. But differ in the case study, findings and the range of coverage and the present study is broader as it covers all the public secondary school in the six educational zones in Imo state.

Afianmagbon, Nwokocha, and Emetaram (2014) looked into how budget preparation procedures were believed to affect the management of secondary schools in Abia State. The outcome demonstrates that secondary school principals in Abia State, have a detrimental influence on secondary school administration. This is a result of the insufficient recruitment of instructors. Additionally, amenities are not given enough attention. The above research focused on the perceived impact of budget preparation procedures on the administration of secondary schools

in Abia State. And data collected were analyzed using frequency distribution and means. The research work is similar to the present study because their directions are towards public secondary school budgeting and from the same zone. While the different in the area of study, population and respondents. (Agbo-Egwu A.O,2019),did a related research on “Impact of financial mismanagement among principals of secondary schools in Benue state Nigeria”. The population was 624 of all junior and senior principals of public secondary schools in Benue state. The findings shows that there are other sources of funding the schools outside government grants and school fees, and these funds generated are not properly administered or accounted for. Also, there is no tangible development in public secondary schools in Benue state and principals are the signatories to the schools account and there is no strict adherence to budgetary plans. The above study was done in Benue State while the present study is done in Imo State.

In Zambia, Daka, Mwala, and Kamfa (2020) conducted an empirical investigation into budget implementation strategies in public institutions. The analysis of the data reveals that although the institution has budget implementation procedures, they are not consistently and successfully implemented. The survey also reveals that the participants were unsure of who had the final say on budget proposals. The above study was done in a higher institution while the present study is done in Public Secondary Schools in Imo State.

Ogboegbulem and Kalu (2013) assessed the secondary school principals’ budgeting procedures in the southeast geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was determined that while principals adhere to the guidelines when creating and implementing budgets, they do not purchase science supplies, maintain school-owned vehicles, buildings, or furniture, host workshops, seminars, or conferences, or engage in budget defence with their bursars. The above review was on the budgeting practices of secondary school while the present study focus on enhanced public secondary school funding through budget planning and implementation in Imo State. The study is similar to the present works as the directions was on budgeting at the secondary schools level ,secondly utilizing the available secondary schools funds to achieve educational goal and objectives. But differ in the case of study and the range of coverage.

(Akinfolarin,2017) carried out a research on analysis of principals managerial competencies for effective management of school resources in secondary schools in Anambra state, Nigeria. The study analyses principals managerial competencies for effective management of school resources in secondary schools. The study found out that secondary school principals in Anambra state do not have managerial competencies in procurement of physical and instructional materials, provision of e-library facilities and equipping classrooms and offices with needed furniture for effective material resource management.

The above study was carried out in Anambra State while the present study is done in Imo state.

3. METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consist of all the 460 public junior and senior secondary school principals from the 302 secondary schools in Imo State. The study was not sampled due to manageable size. The instrument used for data collection was a researcher rating scale titled: “Principals Involvement in Budget Planning and Implementation Scale (PIBPIS)” with 20 items developed by the researcher, prepared in four point scale and were rated by the principals. The instruments were

validated by experts and were found reliable using Cronbach alpha and SPSS version 20 and a coefficient of 0.80 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research question, any items with mean value of 2.50 and above were considered as accepted while items with mean value below 2.50 were rejected. While T- test statistics was used for testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The boundary limits of numbers were used to facilitate decision making.

4. RESULT

Research Question one

1. What are the mean rating scores of principals’ extent of involvement in school budget preparation?

1. **Table 1:** Mean and standard deviation scores of principals on their extent of participation in school budget preparation

S/N	ITEMS	Principals (460)		
		Mean	SD	Decision
1	Make sure that the budget captures the needs and interests of the school	2.47	0.695	Disagreed
2	Prepares guidelines yearly for budget preparation	2.475	0.681	Disagreed
3	Involve the teachers in formation of the budget	2.54	0.635	Agreed
4	Receive and consider budget estimates from various departments of the school	2.22	0.821	Disagreed
5	Conduct orientation for new and old staff to be involved in school budgeting	1.97	1.01	Disagreed
6	Ensure that every school budget needs are adequately touched and provided for	1.925	0.976	Disagreed
7	Submit well prepared statement of expenditure and revenue each year	1.69	0.969	Disagreed
8	Ensure that the budget accommodates the ways and means of funding	2.36	1.109	Agreed
9	Ensure that the budget committee will inform the school board about the needs	2.16	1.084	Disagreed
10	Challenges of the school, and prepare guidelines for budgeting	2.36	0.816	Disagreed
	Cluster Mean	2.22	0.879	Disagreed

Results are presented in tables according to research questions and hypotheses in the study. Table 1 above shows the mean rating scores of the extent of principals’ participation in school budget preparation. The results revealed that principals of public secondary schools participation in school budget preparation is of a low extent. This is because their mean values of 2.22 falls within the mean rating score of low extent. The low standard deviation scores for items indicate closeness in the principal’s responses to the items.

Research Question 2

What are the mean rating scores of principals on the extent of involvement in the effective use of school budget to enhance funding in public secondary schools?

Table 2: Mean rating scores of principals’ on their extent of involvement in the effective use of school budget to enhance funding in the public secondary schools.

S/N	ITEMS	Principals (n=460)		
		Mean	SD	Decision
1	Principals give necessary information to the school board officials for evaluation to enhance funding	2.35	0.781	Disagreed
2	Provide accurate information on the implementation of school budget	2.54	0.591	Agreed
3	Keep records of funds used for checks and balances	2.49	0.669	Disagreed
4	Give room for review of planned budget	2.51	0.665	Disagreed
5	Seeing that the budget has a measurable impact on specified school projects and programmes	2.60	0.586	Agreed
6	Specifying the total number of teaching and non-teaching staff payroll every year	2.60	0.585	Agreed
7	Give accurate population of students class by class	1.95	0.974	Agreed
8	Monitor and evaluate the impact of the instructional programmes	2.00	1.049	Disagreed
9	Promote and protect the welfare and safety of staff	1.85	0.912	Disagreed
10	Ensure prudent management of funds	1.57	1.025	Disagreed
	Cluster Mean	2.25	0.781	Disagreed

Table 2 above shows the mean rating scores of principals on their extent of involvement in the effective use of school budget to enhance funding in the public secondary schools. The results revealed that principals of public secondary schools participate low in the effective use of school budget to enhance funding. This is because their mean values of 2.25 falls within the mean rating score of low extent. The standard deviation shows homogeneity in their responses.

Test of hypotheses

H01: There is no significant difference in the mean rating scores of principals on their extent of participation in school budget preparation.

Table 3: t-test analysis on the mean rating scores of principals on their extent of participation in school budget preparation

Principals	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	Sig	Remark
	460	2.22	0.879	0.1594	458	0.823	Not Sig.

From the t-test analysis in Table 3, the statement of hypothesis 1 is accepted; implying that there is no significant difference in the mean rating scores of principals on their extent of participation in school budget preparation. This is because, the p-value (Sig. = 0.823) is greater than 0.05 alpha level.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean rating scores of principals on their extent of involvement in the effective use of school budget to enhance funding in the public secondary schools.

Table 4: t-test analysis on the mean rating scores of principals on their extent of involvement in the effective use of school budget to enhance funding in the public secondary schools

Principals	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	Sig.	Remark
	460	2.25	0.785	0.109	458	0.805	Not Sig.

From the t-test analysis in Table 4, the statement of hypothesis 2 is accepted; implying that there is no significant difference in the mean rating scores of principals on the extent of involvement in the effective use of school budget to enhance funding in the public secondary schools. This is because, the p-value (Sig. = 0.805) is greater than 0.05 alpha level. T- test is employed here because it is a statistical test that helps to compare the mean of two sets of data to see if there are noticeably different.

4.1. FINDINGS

One of the major findings of the study is that principals of the public secondary schools participate low in school budget preparation. This is because their mean values fall within the mean rating score of low extent. The standard deviation shows homogeneity in their responses. This is not surprising because principals do not ensure that the budget captures the needs and interests of the school, conduct orientation for new and old staff to be involved in school budgeting, ensure that every school needs are adequately touched and provided for, do not submit well prepared statement of expenditure and revenue each year. This is in line with the findings of (Oboegbulem and Kalu,2013) which indicated that principals and bursars to a low extent defend their budget by justifying the estimations of the budget and explaining where necessary. In the same vein, (Asiegbu, and Onyali, 2019), tallies with the present study when they disclosed that some principals and staff do not take part in budget preparation. The study was conducted in south-east, Nigeria in which Imo State is one of the States. This finding is not surprising because budget needs to be approved by relevant authority before it becomes an official operational document of the school. Thus, principals often present and defend their budget before adoption and approval.

Secondly, the study also revealed that principals of public secondary schools in Imo State do not participate effectively in the use of school budget to enhance funding of school projects. This is because their mean values fall within the mean rating score of low extent. The standard deviation shows homogeneity in their responses. Principals' non-participation in the effective use of school budget to enhance funding indicate that the principals do not give necessary information to the school board officials for evaluation to enhance funding, do not provide accurate information on the implementation of school budget, keep records of funds used for checks and balances, do not give room for review of planned budget, seeing that the budget has a measurable impact on specified school projects and programmes, monitor and evaluate the impact of the instructional programmes, promote and protect the welfare and safety of staff and students as well as ensure prudent management of funds. From the t-test analysis in this study, the statement of hypothesis two accepted; implying that there is no significant difference in the mean rating scores of principals on their extent of involvement in the effective use of school budget to enhance funding. This is because, the p-value is greater than alpha level of significance. Therefore, principals participate in the effective use of school budget to enhance funding to a

low extent. This is in accordance with findings of (Oboegbulem and Kalu,2013) who observed that some principals do not follow budgeting procedures in planning and implementation, and do not keep nor use necessary financial account records in secondary schools in South-East States of Nigeria. Deviation from the school budgetary operational guide which establishes procedures and standards for procurement of school facilities appears to contribute to shortage of facilities in secondary schools. In line with the study of (Asiegbu and Onyali, 2019), report showed that most administrators misappropriate school funds. Supporting this, (Asiegbu and Onyali,2019) pointed out that poor budgeting has accounted for the seeming neglect and dilapidation of buildings and infrastructure in greater percentage of secondary schools over a decade. However, the findings corroborate the findings of (Amaikwu and Ofoegbu,2021) who revealed among others that principals' budget planning practices for enhancing financial management in secondary schools include giving priority to the most pressing needs of the school in budgeting planning, setting target to be achieved by the school budget, adhering to official fiscal calendar in budget planning and forecasting expected income in the school budget among others. The agreement in findings could be attributed to location similarity.

5. CONCLUSION

This work aimed at investigating enhanced public secondary school funding through budget planning and implementation in Imo State. From the empirical evidence it was revealed that principals' in Imo State participate to a low extent in school budget preparation, and also in the effective use of school budget to enhance fund. However, principals should be allow to plan and defend their annual school budget and not only the school board. Secondary school principals should estimate their expected income and expenditure in a given fiscal year. This will aid in the realization of school objectives and prevent wastage and misappropriation of fund in the school.

Recommendations

1. The government and the school board should endeavor to include the principals as well as the teachers in terms of preparing budget for the good of the system, because they are directly involved with the teaching and learning activities.
2. The audit section of the Secondary Education Management Board in Imo State should make sure principals record all the financial transactions of the schools in the appropriate account books and present them on demand. This is necessary to ensure transparency and proper accountability of all resources under their care.
3. The Secondary Education Management Boards should make sure that principals defend budget with their bursars always. The government and the Ministry of Education should equip the principals with adequate funds so that they can maintain buildings, provide adequate instructional materials, buy science equipment, organize workshops, seminars and conferences to work up the knowledge of their subordinates every year. This will go a long way to improve the standard and quality of education.

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